

Advanced Hydrokinetic Power – Freestream Gliders

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Whereas traditional hydropower projects captures energy by creating hydraulic head, or gravitational potential, via a dam or diversion, hydrokinetic power generators operate by harnessing energy directly from the flow of rivers. Freestream gliders are a new technology that operate on this principle, flying through the river to generate base-load electricity in a non-invasive, ecologically friendly, and scalable manner.